

Using Comfort Menu to Impact Pain Experience

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Background

- Acute postsurgical pain following spine surgery is common.
- Inadequate pain management leads to chronic pain, increased hospital stay and disability.
- Non-pharmacological interventions (NPIs) can be utilized for management of post-surgical pain.

Purpose Statement

To improve pain indicators and length of stay among postsurgical spine patients through a Comfort Menu of Non-pharmacological Interventions (NPIs).

Comfort Menu

IMPROVING YOUR PAIN

Comfort Items and Services Menu

ACUPUNCTURE

Acupuncture is an alternative therapy that helps relieve pain by putting thin needles into the body.

Acupuncturists can help you with your pain. Treatments are done in your own room.

*Please ask your nurse if you are eligible for this treatment.

VIRTUAL REALITY

Virtual reality goggles transport you to another world and help take your mind off any discomfort.

*Please ask your nurse if you are eligible for this treatment.

MUSIC THERAPY

Listening to music can ease your pain. We can help you tune into a music channel on your TV. We also have music volunteers who can play music and sing for you in your room, depending on availability.

PET (POOCH) THERAPY

Our friendly, trained dogs of all sizes can visit you in your room. Many people find comfort from the warmth and unconditional love that dogs can offer.

HOT/COLD THERAPY

Your nursing team can use hot or cold packs to help relieve your pain.

REIKI AND MEDITATION

Our Spiritual Care Department offers healing reiki or guided meditation sessions in your room.

WANT TO TRY ANY OF OUR SERVICES?

If you are in pain, talk to your care team about trying any of our alternative therapies.

Note. Adapted from "Improving Your Pain Comfort Items and Services Menu", Cedars-Sinai 2018. Copyright 2018 by Cedars-Sinai. Reprinted with permission.

PDSA Model

- Define limitations
- Outline recommendation

- Analyze data
- Document findings
- Describe results

- Identify stakeholders
- Baseline data
- Comfort Menu development

- Comfort Menu implementation
- Data collection

Method

Design: Quality Improvement (QI) project.

Setting & Participants: 28-bed surgical unit in a large California magnet hospital with patients ≥ 16 years, who undergo spine surgery. Baseline data were collected Oct-Dec 2017; and post implementation data between July 16-Sept 16, 2018.

Outcomes:

- Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) pain level
- Morphine Equivalent Daily Dose net (MEDD_n)
- Length of Stay (LOS)
- Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) pain satisfaction score

Baseline vs. Postimplementation % of Change

Note: NRS=Numerical rating scale, MEDD_n=Net Morphine equivalent daily dose, LOS=length of stay, HCAHPS= Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems

Results

- 103 patients were included; 32 (baseline, no NPI used); 71 (post implementation with NPI used)
- Majority had previous spine surgery (baseline 68.75%, post-implementation 67.6%).
- **NRS pain levels** decreased by a percent change of 14.3% (Baseline NRS 7/10 vs. post-implementation NRS 6/10)
- **MEDD_n** decreased by a percent change of 37.9% (Baseline 78.10 mg/day vs. post-implementation 48.53 mg/day)
- **LOS** decreased by a percent change of 44.1% (Baseline 6.56 days vs. post-implementation 3.67 days)
- **HCAHPS pain scores** increased by a percent change of 40.6% (Baseline 71.1% vs. post-implementation 100%)

Discussion

- All pain indicators (NRS, MEDD_n, HCAHPS pain satisfaction score) and LOS improved
- NPI's accessibility may affect its utilization
- Nursing staff recommendation includes consistent patient education of NPIs availability throughout the shift

Limitation

- Outcome assessment of each NPI was not feasible due to limited sample usage
- Retrieval of information (e.g. pain scores, NPI used) was dependent upon nursing documentation
- Multiple initiatives to affect MEDD_n, LOS, and HCAHPS pain satisfaction score were co-occurring

Recommendation

- Consider comfort menu of NPIs as adjuvant treatment in surgical spine pain
- Improve NPI's accessibility to patients
- Further research is needed with diverse populations and large sample

References